

Operational management of autonomous ships: A need for new competence and resilience skills

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Abstract: *The recent introduction of autonomous ships represents a radical and disruptive change in how work is organized in the maritime domain. It will lead to an increased distribution of work and decentralization of control that requires novel forms of collaboration and coordination. This requires new competencies among the various actors. We argue that the dynamic nature of autonomous ship operations requires the actors to handle system variability through a set of resilience skills. This theoretical paper explores how crew resource management training and the seamanship concept may contribute to develop these skills.*

Keywords: *Maritime autonomous surface ships; remote control centres; crew resource management; resilience skills; seamanship*

I. INTRODUCTION

There has been a continuous development in ship automation over several decades. Technological advances in navigation and positioning systems have changed the role of navigators from active controllers to more passive system monitors. The more recent introduction of fully autonomous ships represents a radical and disruptive change, involving ships operating without crews, managed by onshore personnel from remote control centres (RCCs). This means that tasks and responsibilities will be moved from the ship and distributed among several actors in onshore organizations, not only in the RCCs, but also among various maintenance providers, ports, terminals and vessel traffic services [1]. It leads to new ways of communication within and across organizations, different organization structures and interfaces. The development will lead to an increased distribution of work and decentralization of control that requires novel forms of collaboration and coordination [2].

These major sociotechnical changes will require new technical as well as non-technical competence among all the different actors involved in managing autonomous ships, but in particular the RCC operators (RCCOs). With this background, we wish to explore the following research questions:

1. What competencies are important for RCCOs?
2. How can such competence and skills be developed?

We will apply a sociotechnical system approach, involving the view that people and the technological systems they operate should be studied as interrelated. A premise is that the social and technological systems should be aligned and be mutually adapted to ensure good work processes, and in our case, the safety of the total system.

The development of autonomous ships is still in the early days and much of existing research is related to the technological evolution. Only recently has higher levels of automation been adopted to seagoing vessels. This means that there is little empirical data and experience available yet that may shed light on the needed competence of RCCO and possible training schemes. In this paper we therefore explore the research questions from a theoretical perspective.

In the next section, some context will be provided, related to autonomy in the maritime sector, including some examples. Section III is devoted to competence, in terms of standards and a consideration of the relevance of seamanship and resilience skills and crew resource management (CRM). Then we turn to exploring different ways of developing necessary skills (Section IV), before we conclude in the last section.

II. AUTOMATION IN THE MARITIME DOMAIN

Automation is described as the ‘*execution by a machine agent (usually a computer) of a function that was previously carried out by a human*’ [3]. Levels of automation are used to describe to what extent a machine can act on its own ranging from a machine completely controlled by a human to the machine as being fully autonomous and acting without human input [4.] (Sheridan and Parasuraman 2005. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) distinguishes between four degrees of automation related to Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) [5].

- 1) **Ship with automated processes and decision support:** Seafarers are on board to operate and control shipboard systems and functions, some operations may be automated

and at times be unsupervised, but seafarers on board are ready to take control

- 2) **Remotely controlled ship with seafarers on board:** The ship is controlled and operated from another location, onboard seafarers can take control and operate the shipboard systems and functions
- 3) **Remotely controlled ship without seafarers on board:** The ship is controlled and operated from another location.
- 4) **Fully autonomous ship:** The operating system of the ship is able to make decisions and determine actions by itself

These levels can be described as a function of three factors: operations complexity, operator presence and degree of automation [6]. As the tasks are getting more complex, increased interaction and control by the human operator is needed [7]. This implies dynamic levels of automation where the required amount of human interaction depends on the state of the vessel and tasks carried out. Laurinen [8] explains how a ship can be nearly fully autonomous navigating in open seas while in other more complex parts of the voyage it will require close supervision or even full control by human operators. This can also be described as *adaptive automation* where the level and/or type of automation may vary during system operations and where the division of labor between computers and humans is context dependent [4].

Automation in the maritime domain consists of various techniques and practices, many that have existed for decades. For example, automated engine rooms that are monitored and partly controlled from the ships' control room or the computerized dynamic positioning system (DP) for automatic positioning and heading control of a vessel controlled from the bridge. We see an increase in both research and industrial development related to autonomous ships worldwide, but Norway appears to be a pioneering country with extensive initiatives and ongoing automation projects related to short-sea shipping.

There are already several semi-autonomous ships sailing in Norwegian waters. The ferry Bastø 1 operates on a regular route between Moss and Horten in the Oslo fjord and is equipped for autonomous transit and automatic docking. The car ferry Fjord 1 Gloppefjord on the Anda-Lote link on the E39 highway in western Norway uses autocrossing. The electric container vessel Yara Birkeland started to operate November 2021 sailing between from Herøya and Brevik, a distance of 7 NM carrying fertilizer products. All of these vessels have onboard personnel can take control if needed. Other initiatives are still in the planning phase e.g. the short distance ferry Zeabuz and two electric AutoBarges, transporting goods in the Oslo fjord between Moss and Horten operated by the grocery distributor ASKO.

The ASKO AutoBarges and the Yara Birkeland container vessel will be managed by a shore-based RCC operated by Massterly, a joint venture between by Kongsberg Maritime and Wilh Wilhelmsen. The control centre is set up in Horten near

the sailing area for Yara Birkeland. Massterly has started to hire RCC personnel, most of these are navigators and certified master mariners. One of the reasons for employing certified navigators is that the RCCOs in the initial phases of the projects will work both onboard and onshore – both as a safety measure both also to ensure transfer of system knowledge.

The intention of both Yara Birkeland and ASKO is to operate the vessels without personnel and a minimum need for remote control. In cases where the onboard systems cannot safely handle a situation, assistance will be provided by the RCC. The ships will operate at different levels of automation, depending on situation. One specific level of automation may not be applicable to an entire operation, different levels apply to different subtasks or parts of a voyage. This will require RCCOs with an ability to handle variability-both in daily operations but also in non-normal situations.

III. COMPETENCE NEEDED TO HANDLE VARIATIONS IN AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS

DNV has published a standard that describes in quite detail the minimum competence requirements for RCCOs and their ability to support, monitor and control autonomous vessels. It can be applied as a reference document for familiarization, training, course development, and certification. The standard defines competence as the '*capability to apply knowledge and skills with an attitude that support achieving intended and defined results*' [10]. The competence requirements are divided in five main areas: general competencies that include topics such as human factors, safety, security and emergency handling; navigation; engine and machinery; communication; cargo and ballast. A total of 387 requirements are stated in the standard, each related to a level of cognition. The navigators should either know the requirement, or be able to understand, apply or integrate it. The standard emphasizes the need to frequently amend the listed competencies in line with the expected technological and organizational changes. This should be based on an understanding of how different human and non-human actors in the evolving network of control rooms coordinate their work as well as an in-depth knowledge of the social aspects and the professional knowledge needed to coordinate tasks [2].

The level of detailing clearly makes the standard useful for course development, training and certification purposes. Seen in relation to how competence is defined (knowledge, skills and attitudes), the standard is quite explicit on knowledge and skills, but implicit on required attitudes. It would also be challenging to operationalize required attitude within such a framework. In our exploration of competencies needed for remote operators, we thus turn to some of the literature on seamanship, and the 'soft' competencies involved in the concept, and a consideration of their relevance for RCCOs.

A. Resilience skills

RCCOs must be able to handle a variety of factors and be prepared for both the known and unknown to maintain safe operations of the ships they control. Performance variability and adjustment of performance to meet changing conditions are key elements in Resilience Engineering (RE) [10, 11, 12, 13, 14,]. This safety perspective aims to develop ‘*principles and practices that are necessary to enable systems to function in a resilient manner*’ [12, p.7]. It focuses on organizations, teams as well as individuals [15,16] and understand systems safety as the ability to ‘*recognise, adapt to and absorb variations, changes, disturbances, disruptions, and surprises*’ [16, p. 3].

A resilient system consists of four main abilities [17]: the ability to respond to regular and irregular threats in a robust yet flexible manner; the ability to monitor what is going on, including its own performance; the ability to anticipate disruptions, as well as the consequences of adverse events; and the ability to learn from experienced successes and failures. Praetorius et al. [18] highlight that these abilities are mutually dependent and describe how anticipation, responding and monitoring are core tasks in maritime traffic management. Their work demonstrates how learning affects these and the ability to operate under a variety of conditions without major performance drop. Learning is thus the basis for the other abilities and regarded as crucial for resilient performance [10, 15, 17].

Saurin et al. use the term ‘*resilience skills*’ indicating the importance of ‘*individual or team skills of any type necessary to adjust performance, in order to maintain safe and efficient operations during both expected and unexpected situations*’ [15, p. 30]. Wahl et al. [19] studied how simulator-based training of professional deck officers can be used to manage performance variability and present three essential resilience skills 1) the ability to recognize anomalies and solve problems in a flexible manner, (2) the ability to define limits of action through shared knowledge with peers, and (3) the ability to operate a system with confidence. These skills are complementary but also dependent on the technical knowledge of a system operator. Resilience skills can thus be understood as a kind of *non-technical skills*: ‘*the cognitive, social and personal resource skills that complement technical skills, and contribute to safe and efficient task performance*’ [20, p.1]. This indicate that to map the RCCO competence it is necessary to distinguish between technical competencies and the complementary non-technical skills that together contribute to safe and efficient operations. In the maritime domain this can be described as seamanship.

B. Seamanship and building a professional culture

Seamanship is defined as ‘*...a blend of professional knowledge, professional pride, and experience-based common sense*’ [21]. In a review of seamanship, Kongsvik et al. [22] distinguished between three main conceptualizations. First, it relates to *concrete skills* related to the operation of a ship, e.g.,

navigation, handling of anchor cables, maintaining equipment etc. Such skills and abilities are gained through practice [23], and include what has been denoted technical skills. *Sound judgements* are also a dimension in seamanship, involving adaptations to ongoing events, and the ability to deviate from rules and procedures when this is called for. This requires experience and the ability to recognize when blind rule-following can be counterproductive or even dangerous. A third application of seamanship is that it is used to signal a certain kind of *work ethics*, or ‘*...a set of characteristics, attitudes, priorities, and a way of behaving that are required from a proper seaman*’ (ibid: 2). To be social, cooperative, trustworthy and loyal to fellow sailors are valued characteristics, and their importance might be seen in light of the special circumstances for sailors, working together 24/7, sometimes for months, that require behavior and attitudes that reduces social tension [24, 25] (Antonsen 2009; Bye 2015).

Good seamanship is often emphasized in maintaining safety at sea. It is a central aspect of what [26] describe as professional culture ‘*manifested in its members by a sense of community and by the bonds of a common identity*’. They claim that what is learned by being part of a professional culture will have a strong on safe work practice. According to Gherardi is safety knowledge deeply rooted in individual and collective identity and is primarily knowledge that is tacit and taken for granted [27]. She states that ‘*safety is emergent from the working practices of a community; it is a collective knowledgeable doing and is embedded in the practices that perform it*’. Hung and Cheng [28] argue that this enculturation within a community is “learning to be” and different from “learning about”, which can be described as acquiring the technical knowledge needed for ship handling. Seamanship can thus be understood as a combination of technical and non-technical skills and training of maritime personnel needs to address both aspects. Crew resource management (CRM) is a learning scheme that have been used to train professionals in the maritime industry for a long time and that may be applicable to developing RCCO competencies.

IV. HOW TO DEVELOP THE NECESSARY COMPETENCE AND SKILLS?

A. Training Method: Crew Resource Management

Existing training schemes for mariners, are a good starting point for training of RCCOs, including CRM and simulator-based training. CRM was developed as a training concept by the aviation community in the 1970s as a response to the high number of fatal accidents in the industry caused by human error. The intention was to improve flight crews’ non-technical skills in areas such as situation awareness, decision-making, cooperation and leadership [29]. Leadership and teamwork training were initiated in the maritime industry in the 1990s based on the CRM principles [30]. Since 2017 the content of the training is guided by the IMO requirements [31]. The programs are often referred to as BRM (bridge resource management), ERM (engine room resource management) or

HELM (human element, leadership and management). As in aviation, the training started out as classroom-based lectures on relevant subjects, but has evolved into simulator-based training emphasizing application of knowledge in a work environment as well as attitudes.

A non-technical skills taxonomy is often used to pinpoint specific training needs, to structure the CRM training, and to assess individuals [20, 32, 33]. A unique taxonomy needs to be developed for any given profession and adjusted to the sociotechnical system where the work takes place [20, 34]. The skills selected should be considered as particularly important to safe and efficient work performance in the defined operation and should be given specific attention during training. Within the maritime domain there are five sets of skills that are commonly used in training of onboard officers: assertiveness, decision-making, communication, team coordination and situation awareness [34]. These can be adapted to different operation-specific needs and as such be used as tentative framework that needs to be translated and adjusted for the technical and social context that characterizes the work environment of the different actors in an autonomous ship operation.

Much of the training in the maritime domain takes place in bridge or engine room simulators [35, 36], however it is more common to use simulators to practice technical skills than CRM skills [34]. Wahl describes how simulator technology may serve as a necessary backdrop for creating lifelike tasks in a collaborative environment but is not alone a sufficient condition for learning [36]. Social factors are also essential in creating a realistic training environment. Her study indicates that an exact replication of the physical entities of a work environment is not always necessary to realize training goals; rather, it emerges in the interactions among the simulator, the course participants, and the instructor. This indicates that in effective training of RCCOs it is necessary to choose the level of simulation that addresses the training needs, whether this is a lifelike control room simulator, a table top exercises, a desktop simulator or virtual reality tools. However, the chosen simulation method must enable joint reflection and experiential learning [19, 34].

Post-simulation debriefing is regarded a critical component in simulator-based training as it helps trainees develop and integrate insights from simulated tasks into future safe work practice through peer discussions and feedback (IMO 2012). A debriefing provides learning by revisiting critical events in the simulated scenario following a conversational structure (Sellberg 2018; Wahl and Solem 2022). The goal of a debriefing is to explore social or interpersonal frames of action that influence the team's and individuals' performance during the simulated tasks and to bridge professionals' experience between actual work and what is simulated.

B. Training Content

The ongoing development of automation technology in the maritime domain is driven by a wish to provide more efficient

and safer operations and reduce human errors. Sarter et al. found that although the introduction of new automation technology in the aviation industry reduced some types of failures, but also that new types of errors and system breakdowns were introduced by operating a more complex system [38]. They describe how airline pilots needed new knowledge as system operators to detect and recover from errors and handle 'automation surprises' as well as managing new coordination demands. These are issues that also have relevance for the more recent Boeing 737 Max accidents. These are crucial elements also when building the competence among current and future RCCOs.

Unexpected situations that require human intervention are likely to occur in autonomous shipping and the capability to handle these surprises using sound judgement will be a core quality among RCCOs. Unforeseen scenarios will most likely not be covered by the standard operating procedures, and must be handled by some degree of improvisation. This will require an ability to handle system variability which cannot be learned by rigorous training focusing on standardized procedures or known system weaknesses. It will demand a more proactive and flexible training scheme based on joint reflection and operator experience to increase the ability to handle unknown system failures (Wahl et al. 2019). Successful training of RCCOs will demand a combination of what the RE community label Safety-I and Safety -II, giving the training both a reactive and proactive focus. The personnel need to know what has characterized accidents or adverse events in the past so they can prevent them from happening in the future, but at the same time they need to know what they are doing right looking at experienced successes in normal situations or mundane work (Wahl et al. 2020). This adaption to ongoing events or deviates from rules or procedures if needed is of the core qualities in seamanship and essential in the professional cultures we find in risk prone industries [22, 27, 26]

Misunderstanding or lack of understanding caused by the automated systems complexity may lead to serious accidents [4]. Parasuraman and Riley examined the factors that influence how humans may use, misuse, disuse or abuse automation in a sociotechnical system [3]. Why and how automation is used by sharp end operators is influenced by individual differences and factors such as attitudes towards the automation, mental workload, trust and system confidence. Misuse of automation indicates an overreliance on automation, which may result in a failure to monitor the system and decision biases. Common factors that influence automation misuse include workload, reliability and consistency, and the saliency of the status indicators. Disuse is when the automation is neglected or underutilized for example due to reoccurring false alarms and omissions. Automation abuse points to inappropriate application of technology by designers or managers and the tendency to disregard the consequences of changes for human's performance and the operator's authority over the system, it may even lead to increased automation misuse or disuse by the

system operators. RCCOs need to be aware of all of these potential pitfalls when they operate autonomous ships.

Some aspects of seamanship are also clearly of relevance for RCCOs, including concrete skills, sound judgements and work ethics. In RCCs, as in ‘normal’ operation of ships, monotony might be an issue. Life on board, has been compared with life in a prison and the contract period on board as a sentence of imprisonment [39]. In other contexts, we have seen examples of control room personnel with an extensive maritime experience that handle monotony in a good manner. Their background made them more prepared for their monitoring tasks of than others, and led to richer and enhanced interpretation of information in their daily work, compared to others with less seafaring experiences. A maritime background thus seems to be advantageous also for RCCOs, as much of the work will be passive monitoring of operations. In the Norwegian context, the operator of an RCC has hired certified deck officers and experienced master mariners. In the initial phase they need to be certified as they will work onboard in the test periods of the autonomous operations. The University of South East Norway has developed a 10-day pilot course for certification of RCCOs. One requirement for admission to the course is at least two years of navigation experience during the last five years. This indicates that navigator experience is considered vital for RCCOs. Teamwork will also be an important aspect of RCC operations, and cooperation skills and trustworthiness are highly relevant. Still, the 24/7 community that shape the interaction among crew members onboard is not present at RCCs.

The supervision of autonomous ships can thus involve both ‘old’ seamanship skills and ‘new’ skills, e.g., in technological understanding. In general, we can state that a RCCO could benefit from having a long-term membership in a maritime professional culture [23, 26]. When this is the case, the operator has received or experienced a broad set of values, incidents and practices in the maritime career, which in the end appear to be internalized and become a tacit or taken-for-granted part of the person’s interpretation horizon. On face value, seamanship competence seems to be of high relevance for RCCOs. There will clearly be a need for concrete skills, and some of them are also included in the DNV standard. RCCOs will need some additional concrete skills related to the operation of the technological interfaces in the control centre, handling of cyber security events etc.

One can also claim that automation has an element of branding. Existing techniques and practices can be combined in new arrangements and presented as something new. Also, the actual naming used in this connection, is important. The term autonomous may be potentially problematic to apply. Autonomous might be understood as something uncontrollable and that have ‘a will of its own’. In Sweden the governmental ferry company have ordered two autonomous ferries, but they prefer the term Smart ferries, instead of autonomous. The semantics is as we see it highly significant. However, to have

unmanned bridge on board, is genuine a new arrangement. To trust the sensors on board, in combination with sensors/radars on board and on shore, is a new way to operate a vessel

V. CONCLUSIONS

The review above shows that RCCO competency must include both technical and non-technical skills. The DNV standard ‘Competence of remote-control center operators’ is a good starting point in developing a successful training scheme. However, it is important to continuously develop this or similar standards as the operations of autonomous ships evolve. There is little doubt that we need more knowledge about work practice and organizational design in this radical new work environment. In the initial phases of autonomous shipping the competence nested in ‘seamanship’ will be highly relevant to train RCCOs. As the system becomes more standardized and the ships become more autonomous we may see a shift in the recruitment of mariners from extensive experience at the sea to other background needed for the RCCO. This indicate that the competencies built on a maritime professional culture may become different in the future. We think that CRM and simulator-based training must be combined with the technical training of the operators. It is necessary to identify non-technical skills specific to different RCCs and RCCO roles. The complex organization design makes it crucial to provide joint training across teams and organizations. The training provided needs to focus on mundane work as well as emergency situations.

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